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Transcript

Speaker 1

Hello, thank you so much for taking your time to participate in this interview. My name is Anna Makarudze and I'm pursuing a master's in software engineering at Ligon Institute of Technology. And the focus of my research is to investigate how developers and maintainers see vulnerabilities in open source dependencies they input in their projects, especially given the rise of supply chain attack. And just before we focus my studies focusing on five web frameworks, Django, Next.js, Springboot, Daraville, and Rook on Rails. And then before we start, I just want you to let you know that participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw from the interview anytime. We will not retain any personal information or identifiable data, your name and e-mail address and in identifiable details will not be published or shared with anyone. You can skip any questions you're not comfortable answering, and your responses will remain anonymous and will not be linked to the projects you present. The interviews will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow this provider to verify the authenticity of the audit data, after which the data will be deleted.

So before we start, maybe you can start by introducing yourself and maybe the projects that you are a developer, contributor, or maintainer of. That is if you are involved in maintaining the web framework that you are using. If you are just, if you're not a contributor or a maintainer, you can just tell us the web framework that you are using, how many years of experience you have with it, and also how you are using it within your projects.

You can also mention your role, within the organization that you working so that at least we understand how many years of experience you have as a software developer. So is how many years of experience we have with that. Okay, okay.

Speaker 2

Hi, Anna, thanks for having me for this interview.

So I'm a software developer, more on the development side, the use of those libraries and dependencies, less of a maintainer. So yeah, I've been working in the edge education space and the fintech space and. I've been using frameworks like Django. I've used a little bit, but mostly I'm a front end guy where I've used mostly JavaScript frameworks like Next.js, which is one of the frameworks that I think we'll be talking about more in this chat.

And yeah, in my... I hope this interview goes well and I'll be able to assist in whatever I can so that you collect valuable data for your research. Thanks.

Speaker 1

Thank you. Thank you. How many years of experience do you have with Next.js? And also, how many years of experience do you have with software development?

Speaker 2

So I have five years work experience with Next.js. and it's almost 8 years. So I'd say 7 plus is full on software developer.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And then, in your role as a software developer. Do I want to understand what you you said. You're a frontend developer. Do you contribute code to you? Review pull requests or merge pull requests. What are your responsibilities within your project?

Speaker 2

Yes, so mostly my responsibilities differ from project to project, but mostly my responsibilities are more building new features and maintenance of projects. Yeah. So we do, I always do pull requests because it might be a bug fix, maybe feature updates or things like that. So we do do pull requests, we do, yeah, yeah, just the basic git flow, CI/CD flow. Yeah, I'm usually engaged in.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. And okay, the project you are currently working on, is it for a corporate company or? Nonprofit.

Speaker 2

So current project I'm working on, it's for a corporate company. It is for corporate tech.

Speaker 1

All right. And then for the project that you're working on, do you have any anyone responsible for security issues within the project? Or is it handled by the developers themselves?

Speaker 2

Yes. So the advantages with the corporate space is that there's always dedicated teams. So for our projects, for our work to actually reach production, they go through multiple processes or multiple scans, security scans, I would like to call them. And some of these are managed by our DevOps guys which mostly on the deployment side of things, but there are dedicated security teams that also run scans on everything that is going to go online or that is going to go in prod.

Then we do get an audit report from that security team and there's the dev team we work on the issues that have been flagged, if there are any security issues that have been flagged. And we do get those audit reports sent back and we action them based on the recommendations and the reports.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. And other than next to your chairs, do you work with any other web framework that are outside of the JavaScript ecosystem or You are just focused on JavaScript.

Speaker 2

So I do work with Python based frameworks and at the moment and also I do work with Python for backend work. But nowadays I've moved to working with Fast API. So yeah, those are the two major frameworks that I I would say I use on front end. Next.js backend fast API.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And how are security issues managed within your project? Suppose there's a security issue. How is it reported? And how is it managed?

Speaker 2

Okay, so most of the time a A report is sent, what we do is to, there's one guy who gets a report when deployment starts, which is mostly the DevOps guys. They get that report after a whole pipeline has run and finished because in the pipeline running, the security scans based on non-CVEs and things like that.

So yeah, we do get us as the dev team, we get it via the audit, the DevOps guys, because some of the issues will be issues of infrastructure, which are not related, issues which are not related to us. So firstly, it goes to the DevOps guys. And yeah, it's just possible like that from the security team to our internal DevOps. Then if the issue is code related, it then comes to the developers or if it is not it goes to its respective areas.

Like most of the time it's usually code or the infrastructure.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And how aware are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependencies present to your projects?

Speaker 2

Yeah, we are quite aware of those vulnerabilities, but at times we do the sacrifice of just running them or including them. Or in some cases, what in the corporate space they do is they fork it in maybe, for example, it's a NPM package. They would fork it and then they would scan it and when it was in this correct state where it was working and we were sure it has no security issues. We can't really say no zero security issues because there's always that chance of being attacked.

But there's that thing of trying to control your packages where you can have a private NPM registry where you hold your own packages in there private kind of registry and you always help. You are the ones who manage the updates of the package.

You are the ones who request an upgrade and things like that. So it does it. The update just just doesn't happen without you guys knowing. So you got some kind of control if maybe you put it in a private registry, like have some core packages put in a private registry. I know it's not all that would do that, but yeah, that's a step to trying to curb that problem, I think.

Speaker 1

So basically, in under terms you are taking over the maintenance of a dependency. Though without necessarily sharing it out with the outside world.

Speaker 2

The outside world. Yes, yes, yes, yes. It'll be mostly not taking over the maintenance because you won't really change anything. It's just us saying, okay, we're taking a snapshot of this version of this dependency. We always know this is table, this works.

Speaker 1

Yeah. And how aware are you of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects, particularly that they are usually launched through dependencies, which is kind of common in

Speaker 2

I'm I'm I'm not very. I've I've heard about those. I've haven't really maybe experienced. They're more kind of know how the attack really goes. But from, you know, security tutorials, corporate is very up, they always, there's trainings that they have to always make sure everybody's alert and everybody is able to detect those small issues or those small red flags when hacking is happening or something weird might be happening.

So So I might know a bit, but I wouldn't know how it actually goes.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And, how do you identify dependencies with vulnerabilities within your project?

Speaker 2

Yeah, mostly it's those CVE scans. So if there are no non-CVEs for that time, which means the software will be vulnerable to the attack, actually, because mostly it's depending on those non-registries where we just scan against the non-staff and yeah, scan against the non-issues and then... from those scans, we get those reports and things like that.

So yeah, I'm not really that much involved in then checking them, but when I'm working on my individual projects, most of the time developers don't care, which is a problem.

Speaker 1

Okay, in your project, which tools do you use to scan dependencies to ensure that they are not vulnerable?

Speaker 2

So I depend on things like GitHub. So GitHub has a functionality to scan your code base. And I usually get alerts even when I'm relaxed on an old project when a vulnerability was detected or was recorded somewhere on the internet. I do get a notification to say Project X needs a package update and something like that.

Speaker 1

All right. And for the corporate projects you. Are you aware of the security tools that are being used, or it's something that is done by the devops. Yeah.

Speaker 2

I am. Remember, my name an idea for things like SonarQube. Yeah, running security instances, docker instances of SonarQube where your pipeline runs through sonar cube and sonar cube does check for your coding vulnerabilities, non vulnerabilities.

And also, I forget this other one. There's this other open source tool as well, but I think it's paid for. Yeah, but that's one of the major tools that I used in corporate space that I'd say I have, I know teams use and one of the guys in the team have mentioned before.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. And what influences the decision to update to newer versions of dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

What's the question?

Speaker 1

I'm saying what influences the decision to update to newer versions or dependencies within your project? Do you update simply because there is a newer version or do you only update maybe when you have been advised over your vulnerability?

Speaker 2

So usually we update when there is a vulnerability because that's usually a forced update. Like recently Next.js had a very huge vulnerability. So everybody got like a flag even Vercel wasn't allowing you to deploy.

Actually, it was allowing you to auto update, even if it is, yeah, you auto updating in the server, they're even allowing you just so that you don't deploy something with that vulnerability they had mentioned.

So, yeah, we just update based on... No, we just download the version that is currently there. We only update when there's a flag, to be honest. When there's a flag.

Speaker 1

Okay. My next question is, how do you check the maintenance of the dependencies in your project? It's common for open source developers to abandon the projects that they created and move on to other things and stop maintaining them. So how do you know that the dependencies you're using are still being maintained? And in the event of a vulnerability, you can be able to update them? How do you take them maintaining?

Speaker 2

So yeah, in my case, that's the thing where I always see these notifications. Sometimes I even ignore them because I'll be busy. But that's where things like GitHub, that GitHub. Dependabot access the notifications.

Those come into play very much because I get updates all the time from that tool to say, Yo, this is what you need. This is what you need. So but sometimes I don't listen cause I don't care about the project anymore.

Speaker 1

Okay. I see.

Speaker 2

How we, I would keep track of something that maybe I deployed or it's a client's thing where it's still running, but there are some issues that are known. So for those kind of things, I think I would use what you call. I'd use a things like the GitHub tools or the GitLab.

I think it's called Dependabot. There's a name because it always depends. Yeah, Dependabot. Yeah, they dependable, the GitHub Dependabot. And yeah, that's what usually helps me, especially with client projects that are still running because at times I forgot them. And but the code is still linked to my Git e just run an update, then I just push it maybe to the droplet where it's running.

And yeah, now they're up to date.

Speaker 1

And how do you handle the dependencies when-- sometimes it happens that— Dependabot can flag a security issue, but then there's no, there's no update of that dependency to then say you're updating to the next version How do you handle vulnerable dependencies within that instance? Or maybe they are breaking changes being introduced if you have to update.

Speaker 2

So if they're breaking changes and the project is running and it's a need or necessity, there's no way around it. You would have to make the refectors plan for the change, because if it's a major change, like for example, if we already know these are vulnerabilities, like in the corporate space, or do we already propose maybe even for a budget and a timeline to say, okay, this is how much it will need, how much effort is needed for this work, then we'll actually go with the implementation.

If the package is not yet there, most of the time it's more trying to find an alternative package that is properly maintained which is usually what we do in the selecting of our initial packages to the NSF.

Okay, as you select packages, we go for the ones that have active maintainers. Because dependencies that have active maintenance, you know that when a flick comes, one of the guys or one of the contributors or maintainers, when they have their free time, they'll look at it, you know rather than a dead are using a package which is like, I would say, dead project.

There you have problems, cause. Yeah. And most of the time you'll find that when a project dies, and it depends like that in alternative comes where it is fresh maintenance. They're like, okay, we didn't have the code base for this, or just fork it and create a new one where we run it or manage it. Alright.

Speaker 1

And how long does it take to update vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Just you estimate.

Speaker 2

Yeah, in for the front end staff, most of the time, it can be like less than a day. You can do the update. Yeah, mostly when they have vulnerabilities from dependencies, the changes are not that big.

Unless if the whole maybe way the package worked changed, which is usually rare, you might find it's just maybe a hashing algorithm that they just updated using a better one where it won't really affect whatever internal methods or or functions that you were already maybe making yourself.

So you'll find that you just need to update the package version to your higher one. And in your code, nothing much really changes. You know, maybe you just change the naming of one file or things like that. So it's usually things that take less than a day.

But like I said, if there is like functionality changes or things that will affect our functionality, then most of the time it's more us assessing what areas have been affected and what time the devs need to make those necessary effectors.

Speaker 1

Okay. And suppose maybe you know what happens with dependent is you use what you use a library which uses another library which uses another library. And how do you handle

a scenario where one of the dependencies, one of the transitive dependencies is actually vulnerable, but it's being used by one of the dependencies you're using.

Speaker 2

Yeah, so that one is a big one. It's a big one, and I think it's very hard to run away from. I think I was watching a documentary recently, I forget the name, when the Linux kernel was hacked. Because people say you can't, you can't.

But there's this guy who was a proper contributor to the Linux in the Linux platform. But at some point he decided, OK, I'm going to use this. And I think he used the SSH. No, he hacked the SSH tunneling. And everybody was like, the SSH is secure. We know it's secure. Even today, we still use it. But this SSH, it was dependent on this other package that the the maintainer was like, no.

And someone reached out, he's like, can I help you maintain this other package? And they did, but they had malicious intentions. So that one, I think there's no way to really know or run away from it. Because what usually happens with those kind of packages, scans usually miss them.

Yes, scans usually miss on those kind of packages and yeah, it's something happens. Most of the time they're amazed because they're like deep, deep, deep within the dependency, you know. Yeah, your dependency is dependency. So usually it's mostly you can't avoid that. And yeah, it's just a matter of just waiting for the day the walls come crashing.

Speaker 1

Okay. You've mentioned that for dependencies within the NPM, if it's no longer, if it's abandoned and no longer being maintained, you might focus it, put it in a private registry of your own. How difficult is this when the dependency is outside your ecosystem? For example, you say you mentioned using Python. How do you handle a scenario where a Python dependent you are using is no longer being maintained, but you need it within your project?

Speaker 2

Yeah, that's a tricky one. Hey, that's a tricky one. Hey, I think most of the time, hey, that's a tricky one. I'm just trying to think of a scenario like that to say, okay, what would be the actual decision you would make?

Because it's not maintained. No, if it's not maintained in the corporate space, you have to leave it like that. You don't have to use it. You'd rather build those functions that you need from each, which might take time and cost money.

But building will cost less money than using a dependent, especially in the, maybe in the banking sector where you are, dealing with people's information, people's money and people's finance, you can't take this like that because it'll cost the business more over time.

So rather, if it is actually a need, rather we, yeah, rather we let it go and build it ourselves internally. Because, yeah, we can take that risk because taking on that risk could be like too much.

Speaker 1

Okay.

Speaker 2

And take on that risk. Yeah, that's a risky one.

Speaker 1

Okay. Uh, how what practices and tools are in place for, for you to be able to talk, uh, Security attacks such as supply chain attacks in your project. If you have any of any setup that or maybe that you are will that is being done in your company.

Speaker 2

Or any setup. I think it's mostly that one of setting up in our CI/CD pipelines or setting up the tools like our solar cubes in the pipeline where it's not just one too, because I forget the other one, because I think there's an open source one which they also use to check for these things.

But basically these tools run like in the pipeline. And they do a whole scan against maybe a database of vulnerabilities. And yeah, I'm not sure if I'm answering it correctly, answering your question correctly.

But yeah, some of the tools that I mentioned using like SonarQube and yeah. It's, I think it's called open or I forget, but there's a register for CVEs. Yeah, but I forget the name, but there's a container which you pull in. Yeah, I think it's that because when you set up your Jenkins in your task, you point it to that, you point it to the sonar QP instance and things like that. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Oh, okay. And what helps you to address vulnerable dependencies with your project?

Speaker 2

Yeah, it's mostly the security team. It's having to come back to us because you might find us. It's not really like I said before, is Devs most of the time they only care about their code and making sure their code works. And so yeah, us just having good communication between the security team and ask the dev team.

Yeah, that's what actually helps us, you know, in knowing or keeping up to date with what's going on within our code base.

Speaker 1

Okay. And what challenges do you face which hinder you in addressing vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

What challenges do I face?

Speaker 1

That may actually hinder you from addressing vulnerable dependencies within your project.

Speaker 2

So some of the, so in, I'd say challenges, for example, the one you mentioned for where the package is not maybe maintained. For my own project, I'll be like, it's, I just want to make a demo. I can make that kind of decision, you know.

So Those are the kind of trade-offs that you can do or you because you're not, you won't answer to anyone. So those are kind of trade-offs that you do and to make sure that the app works, you're able to do a proper demo and things like that. But yeah, I think that'll be my answer. Yeah, okay.

Speaker 1

So just to follow up to that, just the change, like updating the or rolling back dependence in reducing breaking changes to your code, does it, is it affected that you consider when you are doing, when you're addressing vulnerable dependence, is that it actually stop you from updating the dependence?

Speaker 2

What was the question? I didn't get the question again. What was it?

Speaker 1

Okay, I was saying there's an issue like breaking changes being introduced by you addressing that vulnerable dependent. Is it something that would actually hinder you from addressing the vulnerable dependent within your project?

Speaker 2

Yes, I would believe it is. Yeah.

Speaker 1

And do you have any recommendations for other developers using open source dependencies within their projects that they can maybe some recommendations can give them so that they can manage benefits properly to mitigate supply chain attacks?

Speaker 2

Okay, okay I think mostly going one, one thing I would say is going for stable releases. Don't go for stuff, go for something fully tested. And that is recommended by, by the maker or the creator of the, of the dependency itself.

And what's the other thing I can see to that? Yeah, I think mostly using packages that are up to date also and making sure using the stable versions. Because if you use an unstable version, you never know because the creator also doesn't really know what might happen.

That's why they're still making it as beta or testy, you know, so you can't risk it to just get on a new package. And also on these dependencies, especially if you're open source, go for properly maintained code base. It's a dependency, go and check if it's open source, go and check its GitHub, go and check its activity on GitHub, how last when it was maintained. go and check if they action on open issues, you know, those kind of things, because all those records are usually there attached to the project. And then you make your decision based on that, especially if you're making use of open source items.

Speaker 1

Thank you for the time. I think that's all I had to ask you today. And thanks for taking your time to participate in this interview.

Speaker 2

You are welcome and good luck with the rest of your research.

Speaker 1

Thank you. I'll stop recording now.